

Analysis of Postoperative Surgical Complication in Renal Transplant Recipients at a Tertiary Care CentrePrabaharan¹, V Pravin Kumar², T Gnanasekaran³, G Latha⁴¹Post Graduate in Department of Urology, Madurai Medical College, Madurai²Assistant Professor, Department of Urology, Madurai Medical College, Madurai³Associate Professor and Head of Department, Department of Urology, Madurai Medical College, Madurai⁴Associate Professor, Department of Urology, Madurai Medical College, Madurai

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Abstract:

Renal transplantation is one of the most effective treatment measures in patients with end stage renal disease. This retrospective study included data from hospital records of 62 recipients who underwent renal transplantation at our institute. 17 were live and 45 were deceased donor renal transplantation recipients. Surgical complications such as hematoma in 3(4.8%), urine leak in 1(1.6%), lymphocele in 3(4.8%), ureteric injury in 1(1.6%), ureteric stenosis in 1(1.6%), lymphorrhea in 1(1.6%), graft renal vein thrombosis in 1(1.6%), and abscess in 1(1.6%) patient occurred. The overall incidence of surgical complications in our study is 19.35% majority of the complications that we faced were from the cadaveric transplants. The study reports the successful management of all these twelve patients with necessary intervention.

Keywords: Lymphocele, Deceased donor, transplantation, renal vein thrombosis, percutaneous drainage, graft nephrectomy.

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Introduction

Kidney transplantation is the better option for the treatment of end stage renal disease compared to dialysis [1]. In the past year, we have successfully done over 62 transplant surgeries including live and cadaveric renal transplantations. We are slowly and efficiently striving to make our institute an apex structure in south Tamil Nadu to help renal failure patients and optimize renal care. In the census as mentioned earlier, we have foreseen 45 cadaveric and 17 elective live renal transplantation procedures. We have summarized our experiences in having faced situations in a retrospective view.

Aims and Objectives:

The aims and objectives of our study were to determine the prevalence of different post-renal transplant surgical complications, to analyze various management of surgical complications and graft, as well as patient outcomes.

Methods:

This retrospective study was conducted in the Department of Urology in Madurai medical college, Madurai, Tamil Nadu. The study included all kidney transplant recipients who underwent surgery between January 2023 and April 2024. The study

included both live-related and deceased donor transplant recipients.

Preoperative preparation:

All patients underwent immunological workups such as complement-dependent cytotoxicity, human leukocyte antigen typing, and ABO compatibility before transplantation [2]. All recipient patients were admitted minimum one day prior to surgery. All recipients were dialyzed the day before surgery. Routine blood investigations checked for all patients. As per nephrology protocol, routine immunosuppressants was started preoperatively. Injection antithymocyte globulin 1 mg/kg was given to all deceased donor recipients on the day of transplantation [3].

Operative technique:

All grafts were harvested with intact renal capsules, and adequate periureteric tissue and lymphatics around the hilum were ligated with 3-0 silk. Bench dissection was done for all deceased donor grafts. All recipient surgeries were done on the patient's right side. Modified Gibson's incision was made. The renal vein was anastomosed end-to-side, to the external iliac vein using a continuous 6-0 prolene

[2]. Renal artery was anastomosed end-to-end with internal iliac artery using 6-0 prolene [2]. If internal iliac artery was grossly atheromatous, then external iliac artery anastomoses end to side fashion. Ureter was spatulated and anastomosed with bladder by extra vesical modified Lich–Gregoir technique using 3-0 vicryl [3] and DJ stent was placed in all cases[3]. Pelvic drains were placed in all cases. Foley’s catheters were removed at 7-14 postoperative day and DJ stents in 4-6 weeks.

Postoperative care:

Vitals monitoring, urine output, and drain output were measured at regular interval. Immunosuppressive agents were started as per nephrology protocol. Timely clinical observation and daily serum biochemistry were monitored. Bedside ultrasonography with Doppler were performed for all cases [4]. After discharge, the patient was followed up regu-

larly. Data were collected and put in a master chart in Microsoft Excel format in this study period. All post-transplant recovery data and surgical complications data were plotted. All statistical analyses were done using SPSS software.

Results:

A total of 62 patients were included in this study. These comprised of both live related (17 cases) and deceased organ donor transplant (45 cases) that were performed in a period from January 2023 to April 2024. Majority of the transplant recipient patients were male (56.92%), compared to female recipients (43.07%). But, both in male and female series, majority of the patients belonged to 31–45years age group in this study (males – 43.24%, females – 39.28%). Total of 12 post-transplant surgical complications were recorded in the present series of 62 cases (19.35%)

Figure 1: Pictographic representation of incidence of post-transplant surgical complications

Table 1:

Complications	Number of patients	Treatment
Hematoma	3	Exploration and Hematoma evacuation
Urine leak	1	Conservative management
Lymphocele	3	Percutaneous drainage
Ureteric injury	1	Ureteroureterostomy
Ureteric stenosis	1	Ureteric reimplantation
Renal vein thrombosis	1	Graft Nephrectomy
Lymphorrhoea	1	Conservative management
Abscess	1	Exploration and drainage

Figure 2: Bar diagram representing age distribution among post-transplant patients

Hematoma:

Three patients developed significant hematoma [5] in the early postoperative period. On exploration, hematoma was evacuated, although no active bleeder was identified in two cases. In the third case, there was an arterial sprout leaking from the anastomotic site of the hilar region toward the

transplanted kidney, reinforcing sutures to control the leak and salvage the kidney.

Lymphocele: Three cases of lymphocele [5] formations (2 cadaver and 1 live) were noted in our study. All patients developed perigraft collection between 1-4 weeks. In all cases, a percutaneous drain tube was inserted under ultrasound guidance.

Figure 3: Ultrasonogram of transplant kidney showing lymphocele in the posterior aspect

Urine leak:

A 40-year-old male underwent a deceased donor renal transplant. The intraoperative procedure went uneventfully. On POD-3, the drain tube output was suddenly increased.

Drain fluid analysis suggested urine leak. It was conservatively managed with serial drain output monitoring. Slow decline of drain output from POD-10 and there was no collection around the transplanted kidney in imaging. Patient drain was removed on POD 16.

Lymphorrhea:

38-year-old female patient had an increased drain tube output of around 300 mL/day at the 5th POD. Drain tube fluid analysis showed a triglyceride level of 251 mg/dL, suggesting lymphorrhea [5]. Ultrasound shows no collection. Conservatively man-

aged, drain output became low after 12th POD and drain removed on 18th POD.

Renal vein thrombosis:

A 32-year-old male underwent deceased donor renal transplantation. Patient developed sudden onset hypotension (BP-60/40mmg) with swelling and pain in the graft site with increase in the drain output (400ml -hemorrhagic) on POD 3. An emergency USG revealed perinephric hematoma 410cc and reversal of diastolic flow (RI-1.0). The allograft was found to have lacerations measuring 6x0.5x1cms and 5x0.5x 1cms on the anterior surface with thrombus seen filling the renal vein [5] in its entirety. In view of the hemodynamic instability and the condition of allograft, graft explantation was done. Patient recovered well and discharged on POD-8. HPE was suggestive of acute tubular injury.

Figure 4: Explanted graft shows multiple lacerations over anterior surface with thrombosis in renal vein

Ureteric stenosis:

Figure 5: MRI KUB showing transplant ureter and collecting system dilatation suggestive of lower ureteric stenosis

33yrs old male – Live renal recipient transplantation done 6 months back, now came with complaints of right lower abdominal pain with raised RFT. Ultrasound shows gross hydroureteronephrosis of transplant kidney.

MRI shows hydroureteronephrosis with stenosis at lower ureter near VUJ. Ureteric reimplantation done.

Ureteric injury:

In deceased donor during retrieval accidental injury over ureter and length of the ureter was around 3-4cms. Ureter anastomoses with native right ureter in end to side (Uretero-ureterostomy [6]) fashion after placing DJ stent. Postoperative period was uneventful. DJ stent removed after 6weeks.

Figure 6: Image showing transplant ureter anastomosed to right native ureter

Abscess:

A 44-year-old Female underwent Cadaveric renal transplant surgery with an uneventful intraoperative period. Patient was followed with daily drain output of sero-hemorrhagic fluid ranging from 50 – 100cc. Patient underwent initial USG imaging and was found to have around 60 cc of mixed echogenic collection surrounding the transplanted kidney.

On POD 18 drain became purulent at around 150cc. We did an MRI that showed the multiloculated collection [6] in the right iliopsoas extending to the pelvis along the posterior region of the transplanted kidney towards the bladder (estimated collection – 140cc+ 70cc). Patient underwent elective re-exploration and the abscess was drained around 100ml. Pus sent for culture and sensitivity that revealed to be Klebsiella Patient was discharged with stable vitals.

Discussion

The rate of surgical complications [7] has been reported in a varying range of 4.2% to 35%. The complications in our study were successfully managed with timely intervention. Studies have suggested a higher rate of postoperative complications due to an increasing age-related factor and comorbid conditions in the patients. The incidence of lymphocele [7] in renal transplantation was 1%–26%. Most lymphoceles are asymptomatic and detected during ultrasound. Symptomatic lymphoceles can result in pain, ipsilateral leg swelling, hydronephrosis, and deep vein thrombosis. Lymphocele [7] occur due to inadequate ligation of lymphatics, decapsulation of graft, excess use of steroids, use of heparin and diuretics. In clinically significant recurrence, sclerotherapy with povidone iodine, 5% ethanol, or tetracycline should be considered. In refractory and complicated cases, laparoscopic or open lymphocele fenestration is useful. Hematomas are unavoidable in the immediate postoperative period. Mostly these are small, insignificant and resolve spontaneously. If persistent collection is there percutaneous drainage or open evacuation should be opted. Graft vein thrombosis [8] is due to renal vein kink, compression of vein, infection, graft rejection, Deep vein thrombosis [8], nephrotic syndrome and antiphospholipid antibody syndrome. Ureteric ischemia [7] because of excessive stripping of periureteric tissue has been considered for urine leak. Some other causes for urine leak are lengthy ureter, early removal of Foleys catheter and DJ stent, ureteric twisting or kinking, anastomosis with tension, graft rejection, and failure to reimplant lower polar artery. Preserving

periureteric tissue and leaving shortest length of ureter for tension free bladder anastomosis helps to achieve high distal ureteric blood supply.

Conclusion:

Though the majority of the complications that we faced are from the cadaveric transplant area, the relatively small study population of live recipients lacks significance. We have meticulously studied our postoperative outcome and have undertaken efforts in approaching a patient toward surgery, refining our surgical technique and post-operative care. Efforts taken to eradicate the errors are summarized and discussed in length. In this study, early diagnosis and effective management of surgical complications were associated with both better graft and patient survival.

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